

KO'PHADNI KO'PAYTUVCHILARGA AJRATISH YUZASIDAN BA'ZI METODIK TAVSIYALAR

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada bitta simmetrik ko'phadni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratishning bir necha usullari bayon etilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ko'p o'zgaruvchili ko'phad, ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish, simmetrik ko'phad.

Annotation: This article describes several methods of factoring a single symmetric polynomial.

Keywords: Multivariable polynomial, factorization, symmetric polynomial.

Ushbu maqolada ko'phadni turlicha usullarda ko'paytuvchilarga ajratishga oid bir qancha metodik tavsiyalar berib o'tilgan. Buni bitta misol orqali bayon etamiz.

Bizga quyidagi ko'phad berilgan bo'lib, uni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish talab etilgan bo'lsin:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc \quad (1)$$

1-usul: Qisqa ko'paytirish formulalaridan foydalangan holda ko'paytuvchilarga ajratishga harakat qilamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc &= (a + b)(a^2 - ab + b^2) + c^3 - 3abc = \\ &= (a + b)(a^2 + b^2) - ab(a + b) + c^3 - 2abc - abc = \\ &= ((a + b)(a^2 + b^2) - ab(a + b + c) + c^3 - 2abc = \\ &= (a + b)a^2 + (a + b)b^2 - ab(a + b + c) + ca^2 + cb^2 - ca^2 - cb^2 + c^3 - \\ &- 2abc = a^2(a + b + c) + b^2(a + b + c) - ab(a + b + c) - c(a^2 + b^2 + \\ &+ 2ab - c^2) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 - ab) - c((a + b)^2 - c^2) = \\ &= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 - ab) - c(a + b - c)(a + b + c) = \\ &= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 - ab - ac - bc + c^2) = \\ &= (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac). \end{aligned}$$

2-usul: $a + b + c$ uchhadni kubga ko'tarish formulasidan foydalanamiz, ya'ni

$$\begin{aligned} (a + b + c)^3 &= (a + b)^3 + 3(a + b)^2c + 3(a + b)c^2 + c^3 = \\ &= a^3 + 3a^2b + 3ab^2 + b^3 + 3a^2c + 6abc + 3b^2c + 3ac^2 + 3bc^2 + c^3 \end{aligned}$$

Bunga ko'ra:

$$\begin{aligned} a^3 + b^3 + c^3 + 3ab(a + b + c) + 3bc(a + b + c) + 3ac(a + b + c) - 3abc &= \\ &= (a + b + c)^3 \end{aligned}$$

teglikni hosil qilamiz.

Bu tenglikdan $a^3 + b^3 + c^3$ ni topsak,

$$\begin{aligned} a^3 + b^3 + c^3 &= \\ &= (a + b + c)^3 - 3ab(a + b + c) - 3bc(a + b + c) - 3ac(a + b + c) \\ &+ 3abc \end{aligned}$$

Oxirgi tenglikning chap tomonini (1) tenglikka keltirsak:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc = (a + b + c)^3 - 3ab(a + b + c) - 3bc(a + b + c) - 3ac(a + b + c)$$

Tenglikning o'ng tomonidan umumiy ko'paytuvchilarni qavsdan tashqariga chiqarib:

$$(a + b + c)((a + b + c)^2 - 3ab - 3bc - 3ac) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac)$$

natijani hosil qilamiz.

3-usul: (1) ni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish uchun dastlab $a^3 + b^3$ ni sonlar yig'indisining kubiga keltiramiz:

$$(a + b)^3 - 3a^2b - 3ab^2 + c^3 - 3abc = (a + b)^3 + c^3 - 3ab(a + b + c).$$

sonlar kublarining yig'indisining formulasidan foydalanamiz:

$$(a + b + c)((a + b)^2 - (a + b)c + c^2) - 3ab(a + b + c).$$

umumiy ko'paytuvchilarni qavsdan tashqariga chiqarsak,

$$(a + b + c)(a^2 + 2ab + b^2 + c^2 - ac - bc) - 3ab(a + b + c) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac)$$

natijani olamiz.

4-usul: (1) ko'phadni ko'paytuvchilarga ajratish uchun, ildizlari a, b, c bo'lgan $P(t) = t^3 + pt^2 + qt + r$ yordamchi ko'phadni tuzib olamiz.

U holda:

$$\begin{cases} a^3 + pa^2 + qa + r = 0 \\ b^3 + pb^2 + qb + r = 0 \\ c^3 + pc^2 + qc + r = 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

tengliklar o'rinli bo'ladi.

Umumlashgan Viyet teoremasiga ko'ra:

$$\begin{cases} a + b + c = -p \\ ab + bc + ac = q \\ abc = -r \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

ekani ma'lum. (2) sistemani hadma-had qo'shib yuborsak:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 + p(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) + q(a + b + c) + 3r = 0$$

p, q va r larni o'rniga mos qiymatlarni qo'yib qo'ysak:

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) + (ab + bc + ac)(a + b + c) - 3abc = 0$$

$$a^3 + b^3 + c^3 - 3abc = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2) - (a + b + c)(ab + ac + bc) = (a + b + c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac).$$

natijani olamiz.

5-usul: Qiymati (1) ifodaga teng quyidagi determinantni tuzib olamiz:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} a & b & c \\ c & a & b \\ b & c & a \end{vmatrix} \quad (4)$$

determinant xossasiga ko'ra 2-va 3-ustunlarni 1-ustunga qo'shib, determinant xossasidan foydalansak:

$$A = \begin{vmatrix} a+b+c & b & c \\ a+b+c & a & b \\ a+b+c & c & a \end{vmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$(a+b+c) \begin{vmatrix} 1 & b & c \\ 1 & a & b \\ 1 & c & a \end{vmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$= (a+b+c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac).$$

kelib chiqadi.

6-usul: (1) ifoda simmetrik ko'phad bo'lganligi uchun simmetrik ko'phadlar haqidagi asosiy teoremdan foydalanamiz: (1) ko'phadning eng birinchi hadi a^3 bo'lganligi uchun

$$\begin{array}{c|c|c|c} l_1 & l_2 & l_3 & \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \sigma_3 \\ 3 & 0 & 0 & \sigma_1^3 \\ 2 & 1 & 0 & \sigma_1 \sigma_2 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & \sigma_3 \end{array}$$

bu yerda l_1, l_2, l_3 lar mos nomalumlarni darajalari

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= a + b + c \\ \sigma_2 &= ab + bc + ac \\ \sigma_3 &= abc \end{aligned}$$

bundan (1) ni elementar simmetrik ko'phadlar orqali ifodalasak:

$$f(a, b, c) = \sigma_1^3 + A\sigma_1\sigma_2 + B\sigma_3 \quad (7)$$

a, b, c ga qiymat berib funksiya va elementar simmetrik ko'phad qiymatlarini topsak:

$$\begin{array}{c|c|c|c|c|c|c} a & b & c & f & \sigma_1 & \sigma_2 & \sigma_3 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 3 & 3 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 2 & 2 & 1 & 0 \end{array}$$

Topilgan qiymatlarni (7) ga qo'ysak:

$$0 = 27 + 9A + B \quad \text{bundan esa} \quad 2 = 8 + 2A \quad \text{bo'ladi.}$$

Bu ifodalardan $A = -3, B = 0$ ekanligini topamiz. Natijada:

$$f = \sigma_1^3 - 3\sigma_1\sigma_2 = \sigma_1(\sigma_1^2 - 3\sigma_2)$$

σ lar qiymatlarini olib kelib qo'ysak:

$$\begin{aligned} &(a+b+c)((a+b+c)^2 - 3ab - 3bc - 3ac) \\ &= (a+b+c)(a^2 + b^2 + c^2 - ab - bc - ac) \end{aligned}$$

natija kelib chiqadi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. Кострыкин А.И. Введение в алгебру. М., 1977 г, ст. 495.
2. Курош А.Г. Лекции по общей алгебре. М. Наука, 1976г.
3. Фаддеев Д.К. Лекции по алгебре. М., Наука, 1984, 415 ст.
4. Сборник задач по алгебре под редакцией. А.И. Кострикина М., Наука, 1985г.
5. Хojiyev J., Faynleb A.S. Algebra va sonlar nazariyasi kursi, Toshkent, «O'zbekiston», 2001y.
6. Narzullayev U.X., Soleyev A.S. Algebra va sonlar nazariyasi. I-II qism, Samarkand, 2002.
7. Yunusov A.S., Yunusova D.I. Algebra va sonlar nazariyasidan modul texnologiyasi asosida tayyorlangan nazorat topshiriqlari to'plami. T., TDPU-2004y.
8. Васильева Н.Б. Задачник Кванта по математике. М.: Бюро Квантум, 2005 yil.

9. Копрински С.Ц. Формулы Виета. Квант, 1987 уил.
10. Курляндчик Л., Фомин С. Теорема Виета и вспомогательный многочлен. Квант, 1984 г.
11. Dilobar S. TALABA QIZLARDA AN" ANAVIY BO" LMAGAN SPORT TURLARI BILAN SHUG" ULLANISHNING BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI //Uz-Conferences. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 783-786.
12. Dilobar S. The Importance of Physical Activity in Improving Public Health //Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 16-18.
13. Dilobar S. The Importance of Physical Activity in Improving Population Health //JOURNAL OF SCIENCE, RESEARCH AND TEACHING. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 19-21.
14. ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ ОРҚАЛИ СУҒОРИЛГАН ОЛМА БОҒЛАРИНИНГ ТУПРОҚ АГРОКИМЁВИЙ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ. In Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities (Vol. 2, No. 11, pp. 19-23).
15. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ, (4).
16. Xudayev, I. J., & Tojiyev, S. M. (2023). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G 'O 'ZANI SUG 'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 514-519).
17. Худайев , И., & Тожиев , Ш. (2023). БОҒ ВА УЗУМЗОРЛАРДА ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ЖОРИЙ ҚИЛИШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar, 1(1). извлечено от <https://talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/tvt/article/view/220>
18. Фазлиев Жамолiddин, Тожиев Шерзод, & Холиқов Шарифбек. (2024). СПОСОБЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ВОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В САДАХ. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 520–525. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/110>
19. J.Sh.Fazliev., Sh.M.Tojiyev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>
20. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKTRANLI EGATLARDAN G'O'ZANI SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>